

Voltammetric determination of composition and stability constants of some Pb-amino acids-sulfadiazene (SDZ) complexes

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Abstract : The composition and stability constants of mixed ligand complexes of Pb^{II} ion with some amino acids (L-serine, L-aspartic acid and L-glutamic acid) [X] and sulfadiazene (SDZ) [Y] have been investigated voltammetrically. The reduction of Pb^{II} has been found to be reversible and diffusion controlled involving two electrons in each case. The compositions of all mixed ligand complexes have been found either MXY or MXY₂. The extended method of Schaap and McMasters has been used to evaluate the stability constants of these complexes. By using these stability constants the statistical and electrostatic effects have been discussed. The positive values of mixing constants K_m and stabilization constant K_s indicate that the ternary complexes are more stable than the binary complexes.

Keywords : Voltammetry, sulfadiazene, amino acids.

Amino acids form biologically active complexes, which are important in analytical, biochemical and pharmaceutical fields¹. A study of these complexes may contribute to a better understanding of the type of linkages involved in metal protein interaction¹. Shah studied the binary complexes of Pb^{II} ion with amino acids while ternary complexes of Pb^{II} with amino acids and vitamin B₆ have been described by Gupta *et al.*^{2,3}. Singh *et al.* studied the mixed ligand complexes of Pb^{II} ion with some amino acids and phthalate at DME⁴.

On the other hand sulfadiazene have attracted special attention for their therapeutic importance, since they are used against a wide spectrum of bacterial ailments but also in the treatment of cancer, malaria and leprosy⁵. Sulfadiazene [4-amino-*N*-pyrimidin-2-yl-benzeno-sulfonamide] is one of the mostly used drug of this group employed for wound-healing⁶. Some metal complexes of sulfadiazene have been found more potent than the parent drugs themselves, viz. zinc complexes of sulfadiazene are used as antifungal while silver sulfadiazene is widely used in burn and wound dressing⁷. Narayan investigated the binary complexes of sulfadiazene with Pb^{II} polarographically, while ternary complexes of sulfadiazene with nitrioloacetic acid and different metal ions have studied by Shoukry *et al.*^{7,8}.

However, there is no single reference about the mixed

ligand complexes of Pb^{II} ion with amino acids (L-serine, L-aspartic acid and L-glutamic acid) and sulfadiazene (SDZ). The present paper reports the stability of Pb^{II} complexes with amino acids and sulfadiazene (SDZ) by electrochemical method which is helpful to estimate the proper amount of antidote in case of lead poisoning⁹.

Results

Binary systems :

Firstly formation constants of the simple complexes of Pb^{II} with sulfadiazene and Pb^{II} with amino acids (L-serine, L-aspartic acid and L-glutamic acid) were determined separately by the method of Deford and Hume¹⁰. The plot of $F_0[X]$ vs $[X]$ has an intercept on $F_0[X]$ axis, equal to unity in all the systems called β_0 while the plot of $F_1[X]$ vs $[X]$ gives the value of β_1 . Similarly, the plot of $F_2[X]$ vs $[X]$ is a straight line parallel to $[X]$ axis and is independent to $[X]$ gives the value of β_2 . Here β_0 , β_1 and β_2 are the stepwise formation/stability constants of the complex which has formed by the addition of 0, 1 and 2 molecules of the same ligand to metal ion respectively, which indicates that further complexation is not possible. Thus all the complexing agents under study, form 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes. The half wave potential of Pb^{II} in 0.2 M KNO₃ was measured accurately and was ranged between -0.388 and -0.391 volt vs SCE.

A single well-defined reduction wave was obtained for each case. The plots of E_{de} vs $\log III_d - I$ were linear with a slope of 30 ± 2 mV, showing that the two electrons reduction was reversible and diffusion controlled. The results so obtained are tabulated in Table 1.

Table 1. Stability constants for simple systems

System	$\log \beta_1$	$\log \beta_2$
Pb-SDZ	2.30	4.87
Pb-L-serine	4.80	7.90
Pb-L-aspartic acid	5.90	8.60
Pb-L-glutamic acid	5.60	8.30

Mixed systems :

In mixed systems a ligand displacement technique has been used in which a more complexing species is added to a mixture of a metal ion with weaker complexing species. In such systems, formation of two types of complexes i.e. $[Pb(\text{amino acid})(SDZ)]$ and $[Pb(\text{amino acid})(SDZ)_2]$ have been found where the concentration of weaker ligand (SDZ) was kept constant at two concentrations (0.0002 M and 0.002 M) while varying the concentration of strong ligand (amino acids) in each case. A shift in half wave potential to more negative side with increase in amino acid concentration was observed. This shift in half wave potential is greater in the presence of weaker ligand (SDZ) than in its absence, which signifies mixed ligand formation. A single well-defined wave was obtained in each case. The plots of E_{de} vs $\log III_d - I$ were linear with a slope of 30 ± 2 mV, showing the reduction was reversible. The direct proportionality of the diffusion current to the mercury column indicated that the reduction was entirely diffusion controlled. In all the systems 2.5×10^{-3} M Pb^{II} , 0.2 M KNO_3 and 0.001% Triton X-100 was used.

The extended Schaap and McMasters treatment was applied to evaluate the functions F_{00} , F_{10} and F_{20} ¹¹. These

Scheme 1. Pb-L-serine-SDZ system.

Scheme 2. Pb-L-aspartic acid-SDZ system.

are extended form of Deford and Hume function F_0 , F_1 and F_2 respectively. These functions have been deduced using following equations,

$$F_{00}[X,Y] = \text{Antilog} \left(\frac{0.4343 nF}{RT} \Delta E_{1/2} + \log \frac{I_M}{I_C} \right)$$

$$F_{10} = \left[\frac{F_{00} - A}{[X]} \right] = B + C [X] + D [X]^2$$

$$F_{20} = \left[\frac{F_{10} - B}{[X]} \right] = C + D [X]$$

Leden's graphical extrapolation method has applied on F_{00} , F_{10} and F_{20} respectively to calculate the value of A, B and C which are intercepts of plots between F_{00} vs $[X]$, F_{10} vs $[X]$ and F_{20} vs $[X]$ respectively¹². The stability constants β_{11} and β_{12} were evaluated from the two values of B. The values of stability constants for mixed systems are presented in Table 2. The results are also summarized in the form of Schemes 1–3 where the numerical values indicate the logarithm of the equilibrium constant.

Table 2. Stability constants for mixed systems

System	$\log \beta_{11}$	$\log \beta_{12}$
Pb-L-serine-SDZ	6.92	10.77
Pb-L-aspartic acid-SDZ	7.31	11.93
Pb-L-glutamic acid-SDZ	7.15	11.62

Discussion

Formation of mixed ligand complexes can be explained by considering the Schemes 1–3. The tendency to add $[X]$ ($X = \text{amino acids}$) to $Pb[X]$ and $Pb[Y]$ ($Y = \text{sulfadiazene}$) can be compared. The logarithm value of stability constant of the above complexes are (3.10, 4.62), (2.70, 5.01) and (2.70, 4.85) for Pb-L-serine-SDZ, Pb-L aspartic acid-SDZ and Pb-L-glutamic acid-SDZ systems respectively. It indicates that the addition of weaker ligand (SDZ) is

Scheme 3. Pb-L-glutamic acid-SDZ system.

preferred as compared to the stronger ligands (amino acids). The log K values for the formation of $Pb[XY_2]$ can be compared by the addition of $[X]$ to $Pb[Y]_2$ and $[Y]$ to $Pb[XY]$. The values are (5.90, 3.85), (7.06, 4.62) and (6.75, 4.47) for the Pb-L-serine-SDZ, Pb-L-aspartic acid-SDZ and Pb-L-glutamic acid-SDZ systems respectively. These values show that the addition of $[X]$ is preferred to $Pb[Y]_2$ as compared to the addition of $[Y]$ to $Pb[XY]$ species in the formation of mixed complexes $Pb[XY_2]$.

The higher value of β_{12} than β_{20} shows that ternary complexes i.e. $[PbX(Y)_2]$ are more stable than the binary complexes i.e. $[Pb(X)_2]$. The other stability parameters viz. disproportionation constant K_D , mixing constants log K_M and stabilization constants log K_S have been evaluated by proper equations and found to be (-1.07, -1.15, -1.13), (+0.54, +0.58, +0.56) and (+0.24, +0.28, +0.26) respectively¹³. These results show that the ternary complexes are more stable than the binary complexes.

Experimental

All the chemicals (sulfadiazene, L-serine, L-aspartic acid and L-glutamic acid) used as complexing agent were of A. R. grade and their solutions were prepared in double distilled water. The ionic strength was maintained at 0.2 M in all the systems by using KNO_3 as supporting electrolyte. Triton X-100 of 0.001% in the final solution have been used as maxima suppresser. The temperature was maintained constant throughout the investigations at 303 ± 2 K. The experimental techniques were same as described earlier¹⁴.

Conclusion :

From the above investigations it is found that Pb form two types of ternary stable complexes with amino acids $[X]$ and sulfadiazene (SDZ) $[Y]$ i.e. MXY and MXY_2 out of which MXY_2 is more stable.

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